

Lecturers and Education Experts Perceptions of Private Universities in Mogadishu, Using PESTEL Analysis and AHP

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Abstract

This paper aims to reveal the perception of lecturers and education experts towards private universities in Mogadishu, Somalia by using PESTEL analysis and *Analytical Hierarchy Process* (AHP). The author used Excel, SPSS, and SPSS Modeler for data analysis and cluster model quality as well as RATTLE application and AHP online calculator to determine the optimal number of clusters of the study and the priority Rank of PESTEL factors. The results of the study - from the view of lecturers - explored that the macro-environment that the private universities in Mogadishu operate within is a good support level in their current aims. The results also - in light of the view of education experts - showed the priority rank of PESTEL factors for the private universities in Mogadishu to their current aims; whereas the political factor scored up the priority one, the economic factor recorded second priority, the social factor got third and the legal factor obtained the fourth priority rank, while the technology factor gained the fifth rank and the environmental factor the sixth rank. Finally, the study addressed recommendations around the factors that could contribute to the enhancement of private universities in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Key Words: Lecturers, Education Experts, Perception, Private Universities, , PESTEL , AHP.

Introduction

Before the collapse of the Somali central government, the country has a unique university administered by the central government namely Somali National University offering various scientific disciplines. When the central government collapsed in 1991, an educational gap emerged because of the civil war in this period, as the government's role in providing educational services in its various stages was absent. Early 1992 was when Somali educationalists rearranged again to recover the education sector of the country to provide the education service that our people used to get from the central government that became not functioning at all. Education umbrellas, privately owned schools, institutes, and higher education institutions have been established to fill the education service gap that the ministry of education was provided to the people before 1991. (Plan, 2011).

One of the most important events records for the education history in Somalia is establishing private education sector at various levels; the primary, the secondary, and

the university education tried to fill the educational gap because of the absence of the government role in providing educational service due to the civil war that broke out in 1991. During this period, the Somali diaspora, and international NGOs, and Islamic aid agencies, have made a significant contribution to the rehabilitation and development of the education sector. (The State of Higher Education in Somalia: Privatization, rapid growth, and the need for regulation, 2013).

The tertiary education as privately owned universities was the tedious work for private sector educators. Nevertheless, the community-initiated academic establishments are making tremendous contributions to the higher education sector, particularly in the absence of an effective national government. These initiatives need to be commended as well as appreciated as milestones of achievement realized through community effort and sacrifice. Therefore, the foundation of these initiatives should not be exposed to factors that can fracture it if other matters necessary for the improvement of higher education are not enhanced along with what has already been achieved. (Eno, A. M., Mweseli, N.W.M., & Eno, 2015).

The main needs of higher education in Somalia at present are to reconstruct higher learning institutions to meet well-defined objectives consistent with international standards and to produce qualified human resources. (Amaral et al., 2013). Furthermore, there are great efforts of private universities leadership to enhance the quality of education following the international. Based on that, the Ministry for Education, Culture, and Higher Education has a strategy Plan 2018-2020 for Tertiary Education include increasing youth/adult enrollment, quality standards, establishing Higher Education Commission, and Strengthening the research capacities. (By, 2020):

PESTEL Analysis

The PESTLE is a tool for analyzing the macro-environment that a company, an institution, or an organization operates. It is a strategic analysis process stands for; Political, Economic, Social, Technology, Environmental, and legal. PESTEL analysis incorporates Environmental and Legal elements into the analysis of the macro-environment to identify trends that occur in it. (Science, 2019). PESTEL analysis has two basic functions for a company. The first is that it allows identification of the environment within which the company operates. The second basic function is that it provides data and information that will enable the company to predict situations and circumstances that it might encounter in the future. (Yüksel, 2012).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to explore lecturers and education experts' perceptions of the private universities in Mogadishu based on PESTEL analysis and AHP to determine the extent of the opportunities occur in the macro environment and the priority rank of PESTEL factors to their aims.

Specifically, this study sought to:

1. Discover lecturers' perception of the private universities' circumstances in Mogadishu according to the political factor.
2. Explore lecturers' perception of the private universities' circumstances in Mogadishu according to the economic factor.
3. Investigate lecturers' perception of the private universities' circumstances in Mogadishu according to the social factor.
4. Ascertain lecturers' perception of the private universities' circumstances in Mogadishu according to the technology factor.
5. Determine lecturers' perception of the private universities' circumstances in Mogadishu according to the environmental factor.
6. Find out lecturers' perception of the private universities' circumstances in Mogadishu according to the legal factor.
7. Examine education experts' perception of the priority rank of PESTEL factors for the private universities in Mogadishu to their current aims using the Analytical hierarchy process (AHP).

Methodology

The study is quantitative of the descriptive research survey designed to explore the lecturers and education experts' perceptions of the private Universities in Mogadishu city, Somalia. The random sampling technique was practiced with a sample size of 143 lecturers. The survey questionnaire established by the researcher in the light of the PESTEL model was distributed to obtain the data of this study. The instrument is comprised of two categories. Category one intended to seek personal information from the respondents. Category two was aimed to find information on the PESTEL factors; (i.e. political, economic, socio-culture, technology, environmental and legal) as the macro environment context that the private universities operate within to find out the level of the opportunities and challenges. The sample of the lecturers was asked to show the degree of agreement or disagreement on each item of the questionnaire. Liker' scale was used in the questionnaire where Strongly Agree (SA) stands for 5 points; Agree (A) for 4 points while Neutral 3; Disagree (DA) equals 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) stands for 1 point. For the reliability of the instrument that the researcher established by using SPSS, the result showed a high level of acceptance with ($\alpha=82$). For data analysis, a descriptive analysis was carried out built on means and standard deviations of the items. The weightings of the responses from research questions were computed using means values intervals to determine the level of the macro-environment. The following decisions in the table below were taken:

Table 1. Weighting interval means and decision

Weighting Interval Means	Decision
4.20-5.00	The macro-environment is very good support for the universities' aims.
3.40-4.19	The macro -environment is good support for the universities' aims.
2.60-3.39	The macro -environment is moderate support for the universities' aims.
1.80-2.59	The macro environment is fair supportive for the universities' aims.
1.00-1.79	The macro- environment is poor supportive for the universities' aims.

Besides of the descriptive analysis in SPSS, the researcher used SPSS modeler and RATTLE application to examine and determine the optimal number and the quality cluster of the PESTEL model as well as the convergence reliability; Inter-item Correlation Matrix among items of each factor, and Corrected item-total Correlation among the factors in Pearson correlation analysis in SPSS. The researcher also used AHP Online System–BPMSG calculator to determine the priority judgment among PESTEL factors for private universities in Mogadishu.

Results and Analysis

Table 2. Demographic Data Analysis

Gender	%	Level of Education	%	Monthly Income	%
Male	92	Bachelor	21	200-300	16.8
Female	8	Higher Diploma	2.3	350-500	24.5
Age	%	Master	69.9	550-700	30.8
25-30	45.5	PHD	6.3	750-1000	21.7
31-35	41.3	Experience	%	Above 1000	6.3
36-40	4.2	1-5	54.5	University Ownership	%
41-45	4.9	6-10	34.3	Business Company	17.5
46 and above	4.2	11-15	7	NGO	5.6
		16-20	2.1	Personal	16.8
		Above 20	2.1	Shareholders	39.9
				I don't Know	20.3

The table above shows the demographic data of participants of the study, the male represents 92% and the female 9%, therefore the most lecturers of the private universities in Mogadishu city are male. For the age the most respondents between 25–30 (45.5%) and 31-35 (41%) which means 86.5% of the lecturers of the private universities in Mogadishu aged between 25 -35 years. The level of education of the respondents, 69.9% of them hold master's degrees, 21% bachelor, and 6.3% Ph.D. For the experience of teaching at the university, (54.5%) have 1-5 years of experience and the second rank is (6-10 years) 34.3%. The monthly income of the respondents, the result demonstrates that 30.8% of them gain (550-700 \$), 24.5% obtain (350-500 \$), 21.7% have (750-1000 \$) and 16.8% of them receive monthly (100-300 \$). According to the university ownership, most of the private universities in Mogadishu are property of shareholders 39.9%, 17.5% for the business companies, 16.9% personal property, and 5.6% for the Humanitarian NGO's. However, 20.3% of the participants have no an idea about the ownership of the university they affiliated to.

PESTEL Analysis on the Private Universities in Mogadishu from the view of the Lecturers Political Factor Analysis

Table 3. Lecturers' Perception of the Private Universities in Mogadishu According to the Political

Items	Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	Government's position on the private universities is a supportive.	3.91	.879
Q2	The university is in line with the education policy	3.80	.968
Q3	Ministry of education supports the private universities.	2.80	1.194
Q4	Relationship between MoE and the private universities is strong.	3.06	1.112
Grand Mean		3.39	1.03

The result of data as shown in table 3 revealed that the lecturers' perception of the private universities in Mogadishu according to the political factor had a different interval means. The item 1 and 2 "Government's position on the private universities is supportive" and "the university is in line with the education policy" obtained the highest mean (M=3.91 and 3.80) as a good supportive level of macro environment whereas the items 2 and 4 "Ministry of education supports the private universities" and "Relationship between MoE and the private universities is strong" are a moderate supportive level with (M=2.80 and 3.06). The grand means of all items reached 3.39. This is an overall indication that the private universities in Mogadishu according to the Political factor have a moderate supportive level of the macro-environment for their aims.

Economic Factor Analysis

Table 4. Lecturers' Perception of the Private Universities in Mogadishu According to the Economic Factor

Items	Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	Salary is appropriate	2.69	1.083
Q2	The lecturers receive the salary regularly.	3.70	1.251
Q3	Enrolled Students are able to pay tuition fees	3.50	1.100
Q4	you are planning to seek another business for the economic purpose.	3.55	1.243
Q5	Many secondary graduate students have an economic problem to enroll in the university	3.41	1.152
Q6	The university income based only on the students' fees.	3.86	1.142
Grand mean		3.45	1.16

Table 4 contains the analysis results of lecturers' perception of the private universities in Mogadishu according to the economic factor the means recorded in the table showed a different interval means. The item 6 "The university income based on the students' fees" scored up the highest mean 3.86 with the good supportive level, while the item 1 "Salary is appropriate" obtained the lowest 2.69 as a moderate supportive level of the macro environment. The items 2-5 scored up a good support level.

The grand means of all items reached 3.45. This is an overall indication that the private universities in Mogadishu according to the Economic factor have a good supportive level of the macro-environment for their aims.

Social Factor Analysis

Table 5. Lecturers' Perception of the Private Universities in Mogadishu According to the Social Factor

Items	Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	The university is harmony with the culture	3.84	.853
Q2	The university enjoys community respect.	4.01	.884
Q3	The university provides an equal opportunity for all.	3.45	1.185
Q4	Students' perception of the university is positive.	3.87	.714
Q5	Lecturers' perception of the university is positive.	3.80	.841
Grand Mean		3.79	0.89

Table 5 lists means and std. deviations of the items of lecturers' perception of private universities in Mogadishu according to the social factor. The result of the table revealed that the highest score means obtained by item 2 "the university enjoys community respect" 4.01 with a very good level. The grand means of all items reached 3.79. This is an overall indication that the private universities in Mogadishu according to the Social factor have a good supportive level of the macro-environment for their aims.

Technological Factor Analysis

Table 6. Lecturers' Perception of the Private Universities in Mogadishu According to the Technological

Factor.

Items	Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	The university is technology oriented.	3.63	1.026
Q2	The university in line with the innovation with the modern technology.	3.30	.779
Q3	Technology is widely used in teaching and learning process	3.79	.985
Grand Mean		3.57	0.93

The data in table 4 explored vibrantly the result of the items of lecturers' perception of the private universities in Mogadishu according to the technological factor. The item 6 "Technology is widely used in teaching and learning process" scored up the highest mean 3.79. However, all items have a good support level except item 2 "The University in line with the innovation with the modern technology" obtained a moderate supportive level 3.30. The grand means of all items reached 3.57. This is an overall implication that the private universities in Mogadishu according to the Technological -culture factor have a good supportive level of the macro-environment for their aims.

Environmental Factor Analysis

Table 7. Lecturers' Perception of the Private Universities in Mogadishu According to the

Environmental Factor.

Items	Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	The university location is an appropriate position.	3.42	1.201
Q2	The university building is designed for teaching and learning purposes.	3.20	1.269
Q3	The learning environment is healthy and safe.	3.48	1.150
Q4	The university has its campus.	3.26	1.398
Q5	The university conserves the environment	3.61	.880
Grand Mean		3.39	1.18

Table 7 presents the outcome of the analysis of the items from the lecturers' perception of the private universities in Mogadishu according to the environmental factor. The items of 2 and 4 "The university building is designed for the teaching and learning purpose" and "The university has its campus" have a moderate supportive level with (M=3.20 and 3.26), while the items 1, 3 and 5 "The university location is an appropriate position", "The learning environment is healthy and safe" and "The university conserves the environment" "have a good supportive level of the macro environment with (M=3.42, 3.48 and 3.61). The grand means of all items reached 3.39. This is an overall implication that the private universities in Mogadishu according to the environmental factor have a

good supportive level of the macro-environment for their aims.

Legal Factor Analysis

Table 8. Lecturers' Perception of the Private Universities in Mogadishu According to the Legal Factor.

Items	Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q1	The university is in touch with the Somali education act.	3.59	1.016
Q2	The university accredited by Minister of education.	4.04	.846
Q3	The university internationally recognized.	3.73	.978
Q4	The university has rule and regulation free from the bias.	3.78	.974
Grand Mean		3.78	0.95

Table 8 illustrates the result of the items of lecturers' perception of private universities in Mogadishu according to the legal factor. The items 3 "The university accredited by Minister of education" scored up a very good supportive level of the macro-environment with (M=4.04). The items 1, 3, and 4 "the university is in touch with the Somali education act", "the university internationally recognized" and "the university has rule and regulation-free from the bias" gained (M=3.59, 3.73 and 3.78) as a good level of macro environment. The grand means of all items reached 3.78. This is an overall indication that the private universities in Mogadishu according to the Legal factor has a good supportive level of the macro-environment for their aims.

Results on the Quality of PESTEL Model in the Study

The quality of the PESTEL model has been examined in the SPSS modeler for the model goodness and the predictor importance as well as the RATTLE for determining the optimal number of the clusters. To ensure that, the researcher followed five steps VIZ; reliability analysis, convergent validity, determining an optimal number of clusters and K-means clustering model as illustrated below:

Reliability Analysis

To measure the internal consistency among the items of the study questionnaire, the researcher used SPSS. The Cronbach's alpha showed ($\alpha = 0.82$). According to the general rule of thumb is that a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 and above is good, 0.80 and above is better, and 0.90 and above is best. <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/cronbachs-alpha/>, this result indicates better internal reliability. Thus our reliability analysis suggests that PESTEL questionnaire items applied in this study is internally consistent.

Convergent Validity

Pearson's coefficient of correlation in SPSS was calculated to identify levels of significance among PESTEL factors. The result revealed significant positive correlations extents (0.466-0.786) for all dimensions (Political, Economic, Social, Technology, Environmental and Legal) as shown in table (9) indicates the inter-item correlation matrix, the corrected Item-Total correlation and Cronbach's Alpha of each factor of PESTEL extents (0.726-0.823) as well as (R^2) linear regression (0.7603) in figure (1).

Table 9. Inter-Item Correlation Matrix of PESTEL Factors

	Political	Economic	Social	Technology	Environment	Legal	Corrected Item- Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	R ²
Political	1.000	.326	.487	.384	.393	.495	.526	.809	
Economic		1.000	.368	.399	.374	.410	.466	.823	
Social			1.000	.565	.543	.688	.687	.777	0.7603
Technology				1.000	.554	.595	.657	.801	
Environment					1.000	.698	.664	.800	
Legal						1.000	.786	.762	

Model Summary and Cluster Quality

Table 10. Model Summary

Algorithm	K-Means
Input	6
Clusters	2

The table above shows the K-Means Model Summary and Cluster Quality of the six factors of PESTEL examined in the SPSS modeler. Figure (2) shows the two selected clusters in the RATTLE application.

The figure below demonstrates the cluster quality. *Goodness is a measure of cluster cohesion and separation according to Silhouette which intervals (-1 to 0.2 Poor | 0.2 to 0.5 Fair | 0.5 to 1 Good).* Based on that, the result revealed, (0.5) which is a Fair for the cluster quality model of the study.. Thus, this value is an acceptable level of the quality cluster model.

Figure 3. Cluster Quality

The predictor importance chart indicates the relative importance of each predictor in estimating the model. The sum of the values for all predictors on the display is 1.0. Predictor importance does not relate to model accuracy. It just relates to the importance of each predictor in making a prediction, not whether or not the prediction is accurate (IBM Software Group, 2015). Based on that, the figure (4) displays the relative importance of each factor of the PESTEL in predicting the model for this study. According to the Importance measure of cluster cohesion (0 to 0.2 Poor | 0.2 to 0.6 Fair | 0.6 to 1 Good), Technology, Legal and Environmental factors recorded a Good level of the predictor importance measure in the model while Social, Political and Economic factors scored up a Fair level in predicting the model. However, all factors of PESTEL in making predictions in the study model have an acceptable level of the importance of the prediction.

Figure 4. Predictor Importance

PESTEL Analysis on the Private University in Mogadishu from the view of the Education Experts.

Education expert's judgment by using PESTEL analysis was another method adopted in this study to explore the extent of macro environment contributes as a support or non-supportive factor to the private universities in Mogadishu, and what are the priority factors and challenges surrounding it. The experts were chosen considering their vast experience of the PESTEL factors. The experts examined pairwise comparing among the PESTEL factors regarding to their impotence to the private universities based on the Saaty's 1–9 scale listed in table 11 below.

Table 11. Saaty's 1–9 scale for AHP (Britain & Avenue, 1987).

Intensity of Impotence	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one over another
5	Essential or Strong importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one over another
7	Very strong importance	Activity is strongly favored and its dominance is demonstrated in practice
9	Extreme importance	Extreme importance of one over another affirmed on the highest possible order
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values	Used to represent compromise between the priorities listed above

The priority judgment estimated by the expert was analyzed in AHP Calculator Online System–BPMMSG (Business Performance Management Singapore). The results of the decision matrix and priority rank were demonstrated in table 12.

Table 12. Results of the Decision Matrix and the Priority Rank of PESTEL Factors

	Political	Economic	Social	Technology	Environmental	Legal	Priority %	Rank
Political	1	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	3.00	44.2%	1
Economic	0.25	1	2.00	2.00	4.00	1.00	17.0%	2
Social	0.25	0.50	1	2.00	3.00	1.00	12.6%	3
Technology	0.20	0.50	0.50	1	2.00	1.00	8.9%	5
Environmental	0.17	0.25	0.33	0.50	1	1.00	6.0%	6
Legal	0.33	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1	11.3%	4
Cr =0.042								

The results on table 12 show the decision matrix of PESTEL factors made by the education experts through pairwise comparisons built on their priorities. The experts underlined the political factor as the priority of 44.2% in the macro environment of the private universities in Mogadishu to devote more efforts to strengthen the relationship with the government. The second rank was recorded by the economic factor 17% to seek other resources to enhance the quality of education. The social factor scored up the third rank 12.6% to enforce the communication with the community as the strong stakeholders of the universities to respect their feelings in terms of culture, solving problems, and development. For the legal factor obtained the fourth rank 11.3% because it is essential of the universities legitimate. The technology recorded the fifth rank 8.9% because it helps to make teaching and learning more meaningful. The environment factor has the sixth rank 6% to enhance the health and safety of the learning environment and make the building suitable for the teaching and learning process.

Discussion of the Findings

Built on the objectives and the results of this study, the researcher discusses the main findings found as presented below:

The female lecturers in the private universities in Mogadishu represent 8% to the male lecturers 92%. For Somalia, the number of female teachers at all levels; primary, secondary, and tertiary education are very rare due to the cultural background that professional teaching is not a desirable job for the female. The limited number of female lecturers at the universities in Africa is the educational phenomena, Rathgeber (2003) revealed that almost all African countries, female teaching staff are few and comprise less than 10% of the faculty at the senior professorial level. (Adusah-Karikari, 2008)

Most of the lecturers of the private universities in Mogadishu are between the ages of 25-35 86.8%. This age may be a positive impact on the effectiveness of the lecturers. This result is in line with the findings of Horner, Murray, and Rushton (1989) they opined that the teachers aged between 25-38 are high effectiveness than those 40-54 (Horner, Murray, & Rushton, 1989).

For the degrees of the lectures, 21% bachelor holders as a weakness side, 69.9% master's degree as a positive side, and 6.3% PH. D. To enhance the quality of education depends on the advanced degree of the lecturers which contributes the student's achievement. This result revealed by Zhang (2008) found out the relationship between having an advanced degree and increased student science achievement. (Zhang, 2008).

According to the experience, most of the lecturers have 1-5 years 54.5% for teaching, this is considered as the weak point of the universities and 6-10 years 34.3% as a positive side. However, the relationship between experience years and teacher effectiveness is not leaner as Irvine (2019) opined that the total years of experience and teacher effectiveness, as measured by student achievement gains, is complex, nuanced, and nonlinear. (Irvine, 2019).

Monthly income varies among the lecturers, 41.3% of them gain 200-500 \$while 30.8 % receive 550 -700\$. This variance of the salaries is due to the qualification degree variance among them. However, no doubt that this variance reduces the motivation of lecturers as the study of Mangaleswarasharma, (n.d) found out that the *salary* increases the motivation of the teachers and their job satisfaction (Mangaleswarasharma, n.d.). The variance of the salaries among the lecturers considered as one of the main problems of the private universities (Holzhacker & Yazilita, 2014).

For the private universities ownership, shareholders made up 39.9%, 17.5% for the business companies, 16.9% personal, and 5.6% for the Humanitarian NGOs, while 20.3% of the lecturers have no idea about the ownership of the universities they affiliate for. However, the shareholders are the most owners of private universities in Mogadishu 39.9%, thus misunderstanding among shareholders, mismanagement, and unclearness of the role and responsibilities with lack of the required document of ownership led sometimes- as happened before, to the collapse of the division and fragmentation of the university into two or more universities.

Finding of the hierarchy and rank of the six factors of PESTEL according to the view of the lecturers to determine their supportive level of macro environment for the private universities in Mogadishu city, the weighting means of the six factors indicate that the social and the legal factors obtained the highest scores of the weighting of grand means (M=3.79) for the social and (M= 3.78) for the legal as a good support level. As the second rank, the technological and economic factors have a good support level with (M=3.57 and (3.45) while the political and environmental factors recorded the lowest scores with the same means (M=3.39), therefore we can determine that the political and the environmental factors are moderate support for the private universities in

Mogadishu due to the lack of financial support from the government for the political factor, most university buildings are not designed for the education purpose and rent for the environmental factor.

The overall grand mean of all PESTEL factors scored up 3.56. Thus, we can judge that the macro environment of private universities is good support. For the quality model, the researcher tested it by using SPSS modeler where K-Means cluster modeling revealed according to Silhouette measure of cohesion and separation (0.5) which is a Fair for the cluster quality of the model in this study and the inter-Item Correlation Matrix of PESTEL factors of Pearson's coefficient of correlation in SPSS revealed significant positive correlations with ($R^2=0.7803$) among PESTEL factors. Thus this result is an agreement with the study of Yüksel (2012) who confirmed the relationship among PESTEL factors (Yüksel, 2012).

The Education expert's judgment by using PESTEL analysis was adopted to explore the extent of the macro-environment that contributes as a support or non-supportive factor to the private universities in Mogadishu. The AHP Calculator Online System-BPMSG results revealed the Priority Rank of PESTEL Factors; the political factor is the priority one for the private universities' current aims. This judgment is in line with the result of the lecturers' perception whereas, the political factor weighted as a moderate level of the macro environment. The second rank obtained by the economic factor is also goes - with the result of the lecturers' perception due to the main income of the private universities currently depends on students' tuition fees., to seek other resources. The social factor is the third rank, the legal factor is the fourth rank, the technology fifth, and finally, the environmental factor was given the sixth rank.

Recommendations

Built on the findings of this study, the researcher addresses the following recommendations:

1. Somali Minister of Education, Culture and Higher Education should support the private universities financially and allocate for them enough budget.
2. The private universities in Somalia should enhance the quality of education in terms of teacher professional development, standardizing curriculum, and administration with giving priority to modern technology in collaboration with stakeholders.
3. The private universities have to straighten the relationship with the community on one hand and the relationship with the MoE on the other hand.
4. Each private university should have its own campus/building well designed for the educational purpose rather than rent buildings that most private universities operate within.
5. To avoid the collapse or division of the universities as we experienced the fragmentation of some universities into two or more universities due to the misunderstanding caused by lack of the transparency among shareholders, the study strongly recommends clearness of vision, mission, transparency and roles and responsibilities among the stakeholders according to the rule and regulation documented by the government.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that this was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial interest. Thus, no competing interests exist.

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Dr. Said Abu-Bakr is an associate professor of education, curriculum at Mogadishu University, Somalia. His research areas include educational problems at all levels; primary, secondary and tertiary education as well as educational development in areas; curriculum development, educational technology and teaching and learning strategies. Dr. Said Abu-Bakr has educational articles published in Mogadishu University Journal. He is currently the head of research department at Mogadishu University, Somalia.

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